

The Influence of the Pharmaceutical Industry on Regulatory Agencies, Patient Organizations, and Clinical Guidelines

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Note: This science communication piece is based on the article “*Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the Pharmaceutical Sector*” [1], authored by the same researcher, and derives from the doctoral dissertation “*The Consolidation of the Pharmaceutical Sector in the Global Economy: Growth, Influence, Deviations, and Marketing*” [2].

The global rise of the pharmaceutical industry

Over the past century, since the discovery of penicillin by Alexander Fleming in 1928, the pharmaceutical sector has undergone profound productive, organizational, and political transformations [2]. Companies that were initially small, often family-run and confined to local markets [3], gradually gave way to large multinational corporations valued at hundreds of billions of dollars [4], with global reach [5] and growing influence over scientific agendas, clinical practices, and regulatory arenas [1, 2, 5].

This expansion resulted from a combination of scientific and technological advances – such as the development of new medicines [6, 7, 8] – and broader socioeconomic transformations, including accelerated urbanization, industrial growth, mass production, rising per capita income, expanded access to health systems, and higher levels of education [9, 10]. Together, these factors increased demand for pharmaceuticals and consolidated their centrality as a recurrent response to health problems across diverse social contexts [2].

Beyond these widely recognized drivers, however, critical scholarship has emphasized the pharmaceutical sector’s adoption of controversial corporate influence practices. These dynamics are synthesized in the article under the expression “*Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the pharmaceutical sector*” [1] and organized into eight major analytical categories: (i) lobbying and electoral financing; (ii) influence over regulatory and oversight agencies; (iii) influence on patient organizations; (iv) influence on the development of clinical guidelines; (v) manipulation, selective promotion, and concealment of pharmaceutical research and clinical trials; (vi) ghostwriting; (vii) strategies of diagnostic expansion and disease promotion (disease mongering);

and (viii) financing and provision of benefits to prescribers and institutions, including psychosocial mechanisms and formative dimensions.

Rather than being limited to isolated practices, these mechanisms operate in a structural and institutionalized manner, generating cumulative effects on public policies, regulatory processes, the production and circulation of scientific evidence, clinical guidelines, and therapeutic decision-making.

This scientific report focuses specifically on three of these dimensions: the influence of the pharmaceutical industry on regulatory agencies, patient organizations, and clinical guidelines. Drawing on empirical evidence and case studies, the analysis examines, in a concise and accessible manner, how these mechanisms function and what their implications are for contemporary health systems.

Influence on regulatory and oversight agencies

Drug regulatory agencies occupy a central position in contemporary health systems. They are responsible for assessing the safety, efficacy, and quality of pharmaceuticals prior to market entry, as well as monitoring their effects after approval. Each country or regional bloc maintains its own regulatory authority, such as the European Medicines Agency (EMA), the National Medical Products Administration (NMPA), the Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (PMDA), the South African Health Products Regulatory Authority (SAHPRA), and Brazil's National Health Surveillance Agency (ANVISA).

Within this landscape, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) stands out as one of the most influential regulatory agencies worldwide. Linked to the U.S. Department of Health, the agency operates with an annual budget exceeding US\$3 billion and exerts an influence that extends beyond national borders [11]. Its decisions frequently serve as benchmarks for the approval, restriction, or withdrawal of medicines in numerous countries.

To deliberate on the introduction or continued presence of a pharmaceutical on the market, the FDA does not rely exclusively on its internal technical staff. It also convenes advisory committees composed of external experts, including physicians, pharmacists, researchers, statisticians, industry representatives, consumers, and members of the public. In principle, this plural arrangement is guided by technical impartiality and the public interest.

However, a substantial body of research has raised concerns regarding the integrity of this process. Studies indicate that financial conflicts of interest are common among committee members, encompassing consultancies, donations, and direct investments in companies whose products are under evaluation [12, 13, 14, 15, 16]. In addition, the frequent circulation of professionals between the FDA and the pharmaceutical industry intensifies concerns about regulatory independence [13].

One of the most detailed investigations into this issue was conducted by Peter Lurie, a former FDA official. By analyzing agendas and transcripts from all meetings of the Advisory Committee on Drugs between 2001 and 2004, Lurie found that in 73% of meetings at least one participant had declared a conflict of interest [14]. The financial stakes were considerable: nearly one-fifth of consultancy agreements exceeded US\$10,000; approximately one-quarter of contracts or donations surpassed US\$100,000; and 30% of investments exceeded US\$25,000. Despite this, only 1% of participants were barred from committee service.

Subsequent analyses reported similar findings. Examining 379 meetings held over a 15-year period (1997-2011), involving approximately 1,300 committee members responsible for drug approvals, Pham-Kanter (2014) found that individuals with financial ties to sponsoring companies were more likely to vote favorably on the products under review [15]. These conclusions were reinforced by a systematic review conducted by Nejstgaard et al. (2020), which analyzed 86 clinical guidelines and 629 advisory committee reports [16].

The economic significance of regulatory decisions helps explain pharmaceutical companies' sustained interest in influencing these processes. Authorization to market a single drug can generate billions of dollars

in revenue, benefiting both corporations and investors [4, 8]. It is therefore unsurprising that influence strategies operate behind the scenes of regulatory agencies, advisory committees, and technical councils.

A particularly emblematic case emerged in 2005, when journalists from The New York Times examined the affiliations of FDA advisory committee members who voted to keep two widely used anti-inflammatory drugs – Bextra (valdecoxib) and Vioxx (rofecoxib) – on the market [17]. This decision was made despite scientific evidence indicating a significant increase in cardiovascular risk associated with both medications [18, 19].

The investigation revealed that approximately one-third of the advisors who supported the continued availability of these drugs had conflicts of interest with their manufacturers, Pfizer and Merck [17]. Among the ten advisors with declared ties, nine voted in favor of maintaining the products on the market. Public backlash led to the publication of a critical editorial [20], and under mounting pressure the FDA revised its position: Bextra was withdrawn from the market, and Vioxx, which had already been removed, had its exclusion confirmed.

The repercussions were substantial. The episode undermined the agency's international credibility and reignited debate over corporate influence in health regulation. During its five years on the market, Vioxx was prescribed to more than 80 million patients [21] and generated annual sales of approximately US\$2.5 billion [22]. Bextra, in turn, produced US\$2 billion in revenue in the 2003-2004 biennium alone [23]. These figures underscore the economic magnitude of decisions that are expected, in principle, to be strictly technical.

Influence on patient organizations

The pharmaceutical industry's influence is not confined to regulatory agencies. Another strategic axis involves the funding of patient organizations-nonprofit entities that play an important role in disease awareness, public policy advocacy, research promotion, and access to treatment.

While such financial support can enable relevant activities, it also introduces significant conflicts of interest. Studies conducted across multiple countries indicate that a substantial proportion of patient organizations receive funding from the pharmaceutical industry, often without adequate [24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29].

In the United States, an investigation by McCoy et al., (2017), which analyzed tax records, annual reports, and websites of 104 large patient advocacy organizations, found that 83% reported receiving financial support from pharmaceutical, medical device, or biotechnology companies [24]. In contrast, only one organization explicitly stated that it did not accept industry funding. The absence of clear legal disclosure requirements contributes to the persistence of this opaque environment [30].

Among organizations that disclosed funding amounts, nearly 40% reported receiving at least US\$1 million per year from industry sources [24]. A similar proportion included current or former pharmaceutical executives on their governing boards. Many of these leaders lack direct experience with the diseases represented, receive high salaries, and act to marginalize voices critical of industry practices [31].

Funding priorities also reflect commercial logic. Companies tend to support organizations engaged in “awareness campaigns” [25], public communication, and political advocacy, as well as associations linked to diseases with high market potential, such as cancer, metabolic disorders, endocrine diseases, and infections such as HIV [26]. It is not uncommon for the websites of these entities to display sponsor logos, links to donor companies, and content endorsing specific pharmaceutical products [25, 26].

A paradigmatic case involves AbbVie and its flagship drug Humira (adalimumab). In 2015, the company allocated US\$24.6 million to patient organizations directly related to the drug's use [32]. With a monthly treatment cost of approximately US\$7,000 per patient [33], Humira became a global revenue leader for several consecutive years. Between 2010 and 2022, the drug generated approximately US\$196 billion in revenue, accounting for nearly half of AbbVie's total earnings during this period [34].

The organizations funded by AbbVie, however, remained largely silent regarding Humira's high cost, while actively questioning the safety of biosimilars and supporting legislation that hindered generic competition [32]. In parallel, the company exploited legal loopholes to construct a robust system of market protection. Among the strategies employed were lawsuits against competitors, boycotts, lucrative agreements, and the filing of 311 patents [35], consolidating Humira as one of the most profitable drug franchises in pharmaceutical history.

These cases illustrate how relatively modest financial contributions – when compared to the revenues generated – can function as powerful instruments of political and symbolic influence, yielding multibillion-dollar returns.

Influence on the development of clinical guidelines

The pharmaceutical industry's reach also extends to the development of clinical guidelines – documents that orient health professionals in therapeutic decision-making. Adopted by medical associations across countries, these guidelines exert direct influence on clinical practice, health systems, and prescribing behavior.

An analysis of nearly 15,000 guideline authors published over four decades (1980-2019) found that 45% had at least one financial conflict of interest [36]. This finding reinforces concerns raised since the early 2000s regarding the close relationships between pharmaceutical companies and those responsible for formulating clinical recommendations [37, 38, 39].

The issue is particularly acute in areas involving high-cost therapies, such as oncology. A study examining guidelines for lung, colon, breast, and prostate cancer found that in a single year (2014), 86% of authors (108 out of 125) had financial ties to pharmaceutical companies [40]. The total amount transferred to these 108 professionals reached US\$30.2 million during that year alone.

When guidelines recommend specific medications, the financial implications for pharmaceutical companies can be substantial. If such recommendations are shaped by conflicts of interest, the risks extend beyond economic considerations, potentially compromising patient safety and exerting systemic effects on health systems worldwide.

Final considerations

The evidence presented in this report demonstrates that the pharmaceutical industry's influence on health systems does not occur in an isolated or episodic manner, but rather through an articulated set of mechanisms that permeate regulatory agencies, civil society organizations, and the production of clinical guidance. Institutions designed to protect the public interest – regulatory bodies, patient associations, and clinical guideline committees – prove, to varying degrees, permeable to corporate interests of considerable economic magnitude.

The recurrence of financial conflicts of interest in regulatory committees, the systematic funding of patient organizations, and the close ties between guideline authors and pharmaceutical companies reveal a structural pattern of influence. These arrangements shape not only discrete decisions, such as drug approvals or market withdrawals, but also research agendas, therapeutic priorities, public narratives surrounding disease, and standards of care adopted globally.

At the same time, the cases analyzed highlight the disproportion between the resources invested in influence and the financial returns obtained. Regulatory approval, public advocacy by patient organizations, or favorable recommendations in clinical guidelines can yield multibillion-dollar revenues, helping to explain the industry's sustained engagement in these arenas.

Without questioning the scientific and therapeutic contributions of pharmaceuticals or the advances generated by the industry, this analysis underscores the need to critically examine how economic, institutional, and

political relationships shape decisions with direct consequences for public health. Making these mechanisms visible is an essential step toward strengthening transparency, improving public debate, and addressing the contemporary challenges of health governance in a sector characterized by high profitability, power asymmetries, and extensive global influence – where technical, scientific, and clinical decisions are increasingly intertwined with economic interests.

References

1. STACCIARINI, João Henrique Santana. Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the Pharmaceutical Sector. **SocArXi**, Center for Open Science, 2026. https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/rbysc_v1.
2. STACCIARINI, João Henrique Santana. **The Consolidation of the Pharmaceutical Sector in the Global Economy**: growth, influence, deviations, and marketing. 2023. 145 p. PhD Thesis - Geography, Federal University of Goiás, Goiânia (Brazil), 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10377840>.
3. PINA, Ana Sofia; HUSSAIN, Abid; ROQUE, Ana Cecília A.. An Historical Overview of Drug Discovery. **Methods in Molecular Biology**, [S.L.], p. 3-12, oct. 2009. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-60761-244-5_1.
4. STACCIARINI, João Henrique Santana. The Global Pharmaceutical Sector: numbers and dynamics. **SocArXiv**, Center for Open Science. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/hbs8j>.
5. STACCIARINI, João Henrique Santana. Power, Disputes, and Geopolitics in the Pharmaceutical Sector. **SocArXiv**, Center for Open Science. 2024. https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/z5mf6_v2.
6. MALERBA, Franco; ORSENIGO, Luigi. The evolution of the pharmaceutical industry. **Business History**, [S.L.], v. 57, n. 5, p. 664-687, 3 jun. 2015. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00076791.2014.975119>.
7. DIMASI, Joseph A. et al. Innovation in the pharmaceutical industry: new estimates of r&d costs. **Journal Of Health Economics**, [S.L.], v. 47, p. 20-33, may. 2016. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jhealeco.2016.01.012>.
8. STACCIARINI, João Henrique Santana. Research and Development (R&D) in the Pharmaceutical Sector. **Revista Terceiro Incluído**, [S.L.], v. 14, n. 1, p. 14109, 6 aug. 2024. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5216/teri.v14i1.79594>.
9. TANNOURY, Maya; ATTIEH, Zouhair. The Influence of Emerging Markets on the Pharmaceutical Industry. **Current Therapeutic Research**, [S.L.], v. 86, p. 19-22, 2017. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.curtheres.2017.04.005>.
10. OECD. **Health at a Glance 2021**: OECD indicators. Paris, France: OECD Publishing, 2021. 274 p. <https://doi.org/10.1787/ae3016b9-en>.
11. FDA - Food and Drug Administration (FDA). **Advisory Committees**. Federal agency of the Department of Health and Human Services (USA). 2023. Available: <https://www.fda.gov/advisory-committees>. Accessed on: 10 apr. 2023.
12. HAYES, Michael J.; PRASAD, Vinay. Financial Conflicts of Interest at FDA Drug Advisory Committee Meetings. **Hastings Center Report**, [S.L.], v. 48, n. 2, p. 10-13, mar. 2018. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/hast.833>.
13. HIGHAM, Scott; BERNSTEIN, Lenny. The Drug Industry's Triumph over the DEA. **The Washington Post**. Washington, D.C., U.S. out. 2017. Available: <https://www.washingtonpost.com/graphics/2017/investigations/dea-drug-industry-congress/>. Accessed on: 26 nov. 2025.
14. LURIE, Peter et al. Financial Conflict of Interest Disclosure and Voting Patterns at Food and Drug Administration Drug Advisory Committee Meetings. **JAMA**, v. 295, n. 16, apr. 2006. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.295.16.1921>.
15. PHAM-KANTER, Genevieve. Revisiting Financial Conflicts of Interest in FDA Advisory Committees. **Milbank Quarterly**, [S.L.], v. 92, n. 3, p. 446-470, sep. 2014. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1468-0009.12073>.
16. NEJSTGAARD, Camilla H et al. Association between conflicts of interest and favourable recommendations in clinical guidelines, advisory committee reports, opinion pieces, and narrative reviews: systematic review. **BMJ**, [S.L.], p. 1-12, dec. 2020. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m4234>.
17. HARRIS, Gardiner; BERENSON, Alex. 10 Voters on Panel Backing Pain Pills Had Industry Ties. **The New York Times**. 2005. Available: <https://www.nytimes.com/2005/02/25/politics/10-voters-on-panel-backing-pain-pills-had-industry-ties.html>. Accessed on: 26 nov. 2025.
18. MUKHERJEE, Debabrata et al. Risk of Cardiovascular Events Associated with Selective COX-2 Inhibitors. **Jama**, [S.L.], v. 286, n. 8, p. 954, aug. 2001. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.286.8.954>.

19. GRAHAM, David J et al. Risk of acute myocardial infarction and sudden cardiac death in patients treated with cyclo-oxygenase 2 selective and non-selective non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs: nested case-control study. **The Lancet**, [S.L.], v. 365, n. 9458, p. 475-481, feb. 2005. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(05\)17864-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(05)17864-7).
20. NYT - **The New York Times**. Experts and the Drug Industry. Opinion: Editorial. 2005. Available: <https://www.nytimes.com/2005/03/04/opinion/experts-and-the-drug-industry.html>. Accessed on: 27 oct. 2025.
21. TOPOL, Eric J.. Failing the Public Health – Rofecoxib, Merck, and the FDA. **New England Journal of Medicine**, [S.L.], v. 351, n. 17, p. 1707-1709, oct. 2004. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/nejmp048286>.
22. REUTERS - News Agency. Merck Sees Slightly Higher 2007 Earnings. **The New York Times**. 2006. Available: <https://www.nytimes.com/2006/12/07/business/07drug.html>. Accessed on: 27 oct. 2025.
23. PFIZER - Financial Report (2004). New York, NY: **Pfizer**, 2005. 67 p. Available: https://truecostofhealthcare.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/Pfizer_2004.87220720.pdf. Accessed on: 10 abr. 2023.
24. MCCOY, Matthew S. et al. Conflicts of Interest for Patient-Advocacy Organizations. **New England Journal of Medicine**, [S.L.], v. 376, n. 9, p. 880-885, 2 mar. 2017. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/nejmsr1610625>.
25. LEXCHIN, Joel et al. National patient groups in Canada and their disclosure of relationships with pharmaceutical companies: a cross-sectional study. **BMJ Open**, v. 12, n. 3, mar. 2022. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-055287>.
26. OZIERANSKI, Piotr et al. Exposing drug industry funding of UK patient organisations. **BMJ**, [S.L.], p. 1-9, 22 may. 2019. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.11806>.
27. COLOMBO, Cinzia et al. Patient Organizations Funding from Pharmaceutical Companies: is disclosure clear, complete and accessible to the public? an Italian survey. **Plos One**, v. 7, n. 5. 2012. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0034974>.
28. HEMMINKI, Elina et al. Co-operation between patient organisations and the drug industry in Finland. **Social Science & Medicine**, [S.L.], v. 70, n. 8, p. 1171, apr. 2010. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2010.01.005>.
29. MULINARI, Shai et al. Five years of pharmaceutical industry funding of patient organisations in Sweden: cross-sectional study of companies, patient organisations and drugs. **Plos One**, v. 15, n. 6, jun. 2020. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0235021>.
30. KARAS, Laura et al. Pharmaceutical Industry Funding to Patient-Advocacy Organization: a cross-national comparison of disclosure codes and regulation. **Hastings International and Comparative Law Review**, EUA, v. 42, n. 2, p. 453, mar. 2019. Available: https://repository.uchastings.edu/hastings_international_comparative_law_review/vol42/iss2/3/. Accessed on: 26 nov. 2025.
31. BATT, Sharon. How Big Pharma hijacked patient groups to keep drug prices high. **The Breach**. 2022. Available: <https://breachmedia.ca/how-big-pharma-took-over-patient-groups-to-keep-drug-prices-high/>. Accessed on: 28 nov. 2025.
32. KOPP, Emily et al. Patient Advocacy Groups Take in Millions from Drugmakers. Is There a Payback? **KFF Health News**. 2018. Available: <https://kffhealthnews.org/news/patient-advocacy-groups-take-in-millions-from-drugmakers-is-there-a-payback/>. Accessed on: 26 nov. 2025.
33. GOODRX - American healthcare company. Humira (adalimumab): Basics, Side Effects, Reviews & More. 2023. Available: <https://www.goodrx.com/humira/what-is>. Acesso em: 17 apr. 2023.
34. ABBVIE - **Annual Reports** (2010 - 2022). North Chicago, Illinois, EUA: AbbVie, 2023. Available: <https://investors.abbvie.com/annual-report-proxy>. Accessed on: 17 apr. 2023.
35. ROBBINS, Rebecca. How a Drug Company Made \$114 Billion by Gaming the U.S. Patent System. **The New York Times**. 2023. Available: <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/01/28/business/humira-abbvie-monopoly.html>. Accessed on: 27 oct. 2025.
36. TABATABAVAKILI, Sahar et al. Financial Conflicts of Interest in Clinical Practice Guidelines: a systematic review. **Mayo Clinic Proceedings**, v. 5, n. 2, p. 466-475, apr. 2021. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.mayocpiqo.2020.09.016>.
37. CHOUDHRY, Niteesh K. et al. Relationships Between Authors of Clinical Practice Guidelines and the Pharmaceutical Industry. **Jama**, [S.L.], v. 287, n. 5, p. 612, feb. 2002. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.287.5.612>.
38. NEUMAN, J. et al. Prevalence of financial conflicts of interest among panel members producing clinical practice guidelines in Canada and United States: cross sectional study. **BMJ**, v. 343, n. 112, p. 1-8, oct. 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d5621>.
39. BINDSLEV, Julie Bolette Brix et al. Underreporting of conflicts of interest in clinical practice guidelines: cross sectional study. **BMC Medical Ethics**, [S.L.], v. 14, n. 1, p. 1, 3 may. 2013. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1472-6939-14-19>.
40. MITCHELL, Aaron P. et al. Financial Relationships with Industry Among National Comprehensive Cancer Network Guideline Authors. **Jama Oncology**, v. 2, n. 12, p. 1628, dec. 2016. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamaoncol.2016.2710>.